

“ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MODIFIED ABCD BUNDLE ON ICU PSYCHOSIS AMONG POST-OPERATIVE CARDIAC PATIENTS.”

Ms. Preeti Kunte^{1*}, Dr. Vishwanath Biradar²

1. MSC student, Medical Surgical Nursing (CCN), MGM's Mother Teresa CON.
2. Associate Professor, MSN, MGM's Mother Teresa CON.

Received: Sep 15, 2025

Accepted: Oct 08, 2025

Published: Oct 09, 2025

ABSTRACT

Background: Many patients face significant challenges during the post operative period including pain, anxiety and sleep disturbances which can lead into ICU psychosis. According to American Psychiatric Association's Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM), ICU psychosis is a disturbance of cognition and consciousness that develops over a short duration of time and fluctuates over time This can be prevented by early assessment, diagnosis and treatment. The nurse – patient relationship is one of the keystones in preventing ICU psychosis. Supportive approach by the health care team may be quite helpful in patient's rehabilitation. Studies have emphasized on use of introductory in-services and educational intervention and implementation of tools for evaluation of ICU psychosis to improve quality of care for ICU Patients.

Methodology: The research design used in this study was true experimental post-test only control group design with 70 samples using simple random sampling technique, with 35 each in the experimental and control group. The informed consent was obtained. The patients in the experimental group were administered the modified ABCD bundle. Awakening aspect of orientation was given to the patients during the pre-operative day, whereas the other components were given during the post-operative period. The patients in the control group were administered with hospital routine care. The post-test level of ICU psychosis was assessed using the Intensive Care Delirium Screening Checklist. The post-test I was conducted on the 2nd POD and the posttest II was conducted on the 4th POD. Both the post-test levels of ICU psychosis were measured using ICDSC. The data were coded and entered in the main coding sheet.

Results: The study result reveals that, 2nd day observation on ICU psychosis; mean score in experimental group was 1.74 with SD 1.50, whereas in control group mean score was 3.03 with SD 1.69. The calculated unpaired t value was 3.36 and p value is 0.001. By conventional criteria this difference is considered to be statistically significant and observation were recorded on 4th day and it reveals that, the mean score in experimental group 0.54 with SD 0.98, whereas in control group mean score was 3.11 with SD 1.81. The calculated unpaired t value was 7.38 and $p = 0.0001$. It concludes at 5% level of significance and 68 degrees of freedom that the above data gives sufficient evidence that after receiving ABCD bundle care among experimental group, ICU psychosis among post operative cardiac patients was lower with compared to control group. Study proved that modified ABCD bundle had sustained significant impact on the level of ICU psychosis among the post-operative cardiac patients. The paired 't' test revealed that there is high level of statistical significance between the post-test I and post-test II level of ICU psychosis in the experimental group. The findings also revealed that t statistically significant association was found between the post-test I level of ICU psychosis among experimental group with regard to educational status ($p=0.002$), the post-test I level of ICU psychosis among control group and educational status ($p = 0.003$), occupation ($p = 0.03$) monthly income ($p = 0.000$). Hence null hypothesis is rejected and accepted research hypothesis.

Conclusion: *The findings verified that modified ABCD bundle was very effective in reducing the level of ICU psychosis of patients who underwent cardiac surgery and can be used as a non-pharmacological measure to reduce ICU psychosis during ICU stay.*

Keywords : *ICU psychosis; Modified ABCD bundle; post operative cardiac patients; effectiveness.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental and physical health's are probably the two most frequently discussed types of health. Many patients face significant challenges during the post operative period including pain, anxiety and sleep disturbances which can lead into ICU psychosis.² According to American Psychiatric Association's Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM), ICU psychosis is a disturbance of cognition and consciousness that develops over a short duration of time and fluctuates over time. The different terms used to describe ICU psychosis are, delirium, ICU syndrome, acute brain failure and acute confusional state.⁴

This can be prevented by early assessment, diagnosis and treatment. The nurse – patient relationship is one of the keystones in preventing ICU psychosis. Supportive approach by the health care team may be quite helpful in patient's rehabilitation. Studies have emphasized on use of introductory in-services and educational intervention and implementation of tools for evaluation of ICU psychosis to improve quality of care for ICU Patients.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This True – Experimental post-test only control group research study was carried out on post operative cardiac patients at selected 02 hospitals in the city from last week December 2021 to January 2022. A total 70 post operative cardiac patients who fulfill the inclusion criteria were for in this study.

Research design – True – Experimental post-test only control group research design.

Study Location: The researcher conducted the study at adult ICU (CVTS) which was 07 bedded post-operative ICU, at Mahatma Gandhi Mission Hospital and AIIMS hospital at Aurangabad. It is 750 bedded and 300 bedded multi-specialty hospitals.

Study Duration: last week December 2021 to January 2022.

Sample size: 70 patients.

Sample size calculation: Calculation of sample size:

70 (35 in experimental and 35 in control group)

$$n = 2 \frac{S^2(Z_1+Z_2)^2}{(M_1-M_2)^2}$$

$$2 ([1.4] ^2 (2.32+2.32) ^2)/(1.20- 3.23)^2$$

$$= 21$$

The total sample consisted of 70 post-operative cardiac patients (35 in study group and 35 in control group)

Subjects & selection method: In the current research target population was all the post-operative cardiac patients who had undergone cardiac surgeries like coronary artery bypass graft - on pump, coronary artery bypass graft - off pump, valve replacement or valve repair surgeries in the city.

In this study, sampling technique used was Simple Random Sampling Technique. In that lottery method is used. the samples were all the postoperative cardiac patients, who had undergone cardiac surgeries in at Mahatma Gandhi Mission and AIIMS Hospital, who fulfilled the sample selection criteria. The total sample consisted of 70 post-operative cardiac patients (35 in study group and 35 in control group).

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients who were between the age group of 20 to 80 years.

2. Patients who had undergone cardiac surgeries first time.
3. Patients who were willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients who are in an unconscious state.
2. Patients who are not extubated from mechanical ventilators within 24 hours.
3. Patients with history of psychiatric illness.
4. Patients who are on Antianxiolytic, Antipsychotic drugs.

Procedure methodology

The data collection procedure was conducted after obtaining ethical committee clearance from the selected Hospitals of city. The collection of data carried out from last week December 2021 to January 2022. A formal written permission was sought from the Director of Cardio-thoracic surgery, Medical Superintendent and official information was given to Nursing Superintendent, In-charges of CVTS and cardiac wards.

Samples were selected and allocated to experimental and control group by using simple random sampling method in that by lottery method. The samples were given adequate explanation about the self and the study. Written and oral consent was obtained from both patients and their relatives. Anonymity and confidentiality about the responses was assured. The data were collected under three phases.

Phase -I - Demographic data of the selected samples were collected on the pre-operative day that is a day before surgery followed by for the experimental group. The intervention protocol modified ABCD bundle's component "Awakening" was administered along with hospital routine care. The patients were explained that the intervention will be continued in the 1st post-operative day onwards.

Phase-II - During the first post-operative day the awakening component which highlights about the orientation was administered. Immediately after the extubation or on 2nd postoperative day, the other components of modified ABCD bundle that is breathing, cognitive stimulating activities and daily exercises were initiated and continued till 4th post-operative day. For the control group hospital routine care was only carried out.

Phase-III- During the 2nd post-operative day, the post-test I assessment which identifies the level of ICU psychosis, among post-operative cardiac patients, of both experimental and control group, by using intensive care delirium screening checklist was done. During the 4th post-operative day, the post-test II assessment which identifies the level of ICU psychosis, among post-operative cardiac patients, of both experimental and control group, by using intensive care delirium screening checklist was administered. The collected data were tabulated for analysis and analyzed by using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Statistical analysis

Analysis and interpretation of the data were carried out by using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency and percentage distribution was used to analyze the demographic data; Frequency, percentage distribution, means and standard deviation was used to assess the prevalence of ICU psychosis among post-operative cardiac patients. Paired t – test and Unpaired t-test was used to assess the effectiveness of modified ABCD bundle on ICU psychosis. Chi-square test was used to associate the post-test level of ICU psychosis among post-operative cardiac patients with their selected demographic variables of experimental and control group. The level $P < 0.05$ was considered as the cutoff value or significance.

III. RESULT

Section -1: Assessment of level of ICU psychosis among the post-operative cardiac patients in the experimental and control group

Table 1- Frequency and percentage distribution of level of ICU psychosis among post operative cardiac patients in experimental and control group. N= (35+35)70

Level of ICU psychosis	Score	Experimental Group		Control Group	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	0	7	20.00	1	2.85
Sub-syndromal delirium	1-3	22	62.85	22	62.85
Delirium	4-8	6	17.14	12	34.28
Total		35	100%	35	100%

Figure No 1: Distribution of samples according to level of ICU psychosis

The table no 1 and figure no 1 shows that, on 2nd day observation, majority 22(62.85%) in experimental group and control group had sub-syndromal delirium, 6(17.14%) in experimental group, 12(34.28%) in control group had delirium and 7(20%) in experimental group and 1(2.85%) in control group had no any ICU psychosis.

Table 2- Frequency and percentage distribution of level of ICU psychosis among post operative cardiac patients in experimental and control group. N= (35+35)70

Level of ICU psychosis	Score	Experimental Group		Control Group	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	0	24	68.57	1	2.85
Sub-syndromal delirium	1-3	10	28.57	19	54.28
Delirium	4-8	1	2.85	15	42.85
TOTAL		35	100	35	100

Figure No 2: Distribution of samples according to level of ICU Psychosis

The table no 2 and figure no 2 shows that, on 4th day observation, majority 24 (68.57%) in experimental group and only 1 (2.85%) control group had no ICU psychosis, 10 (28.57%) in experimental and 19 (54.28%) control group had sub-syndromal delirium, 1 (2.85%) in experimental group, 15(42.85%) in control group had delirium.

Section -2: Assessment of modified ABCD bundle on level ICU psychosis among post-operative cardiac patients in experimental group.

This section depicted the analysis and interpretation of effect of ABCD bundle on ICU psychosis among post operative cardiac patients in experimental group

Table No 3. Assessment of effectiveness modified ABCD bundle on ICU psychosis among post-operative cardiac patients in experimental group. (2nd and 4th day observation). N=35

Particular		Mean	SD	SEM	t-test value	p-value
Experimental Group	2 nd day observation	1.74	1.50	0.25	6.00	P<0.0001 (Significant)
	4 th day observation	0.54	0.98	0.17		

The table no.3 shows that on 4th day observation mean ICU psychosis score was lower 0.54 with SD ±0.98 when it compared with 2nd day observation mean score 1.74 with SD ±1.50 in experimental group. It shows that with ABCD bundle intervention mean level was reduced to 1.20. The statistical paired t test illustrates t value6.00, p <0.0001. The difference in level of 2nd day and 4th day observation found statistically significant at 0.05% level in experimental group. It concludes at 5% level of significance and 34 degrees of freedom that the above data gives sufficient evidence to conclude that patients after receiving ABCD bundle of care is effective in preventing ICU psychosis. Hence reject null hypothesis and accept research hypothesis.

Compare the effects of modified ABCD bundle on ICU psychosis among experimental and control group.

Table No 4. Comparisons of effect of modified ABCD bundle on ICU psychosis among experimental and control group N=70

Particulars		Mean	SD	SEM	T value	P-value
2 nd day observation	Experimental Group	1.74	1.50	0.25	3.36	P=0.001* S
	Control Group	3.03	1.69	0.29		
4 th day observation	Experimental Group	0.54	0.98	0.17	7.38	P<0.0001* S
	Control Group	3.11	1.81	.031		

NS= Non significant; S= Significant

Table no 4 depicts that in 2nd day observation on ICU psychosis, mean score in experimental group was 1.74 with SD 1.50, whereas in control group mean score was 3.03 with SD 1.69. The calculated unpaired t value was 3.36 and p value is 0.001. By conventional criteria this difference is considered to be statistically significant.

The table 4 also illustrates that, observation was recorded on 4th day and it reveals that, the mean score in experimental group 0.54 with SD 0.98, whereas in control group mean score was 3.11 with SD 1.81. The calculated unpaired t value was 7.38 and $p < 0.0001$. It concludes at 5% level of significance and 68 degrees of freedom that the above data gives sufficient evidence that after receiving ABCD bundle care among experimental group, ICU psychosis among post operative cardiac patients was lower with compared to control group. Hence null hypothesis is rejected.

Section -3: Association between level of ICU psychosis among experimental group with selected demographic variable.

Table no 5: Association between level of ICU psychosis (2nd Day observation) with demographic variables among post operative cardiac patient under experimental group. N=35

Sr. No.	Demographic Variables	Level of ICU Psychosis						df	Chi square Value	P Value	Significance
		Normal		Sub syndromal		Delirium					
		F	%	F	%	F	%				
1	Age in Years										
	20-35	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	4	4.706	0.319	Not significant
	36-50	3	8.57	5	14.29	0	0.00				
	51-65	3	8.57	8	22.86	4	11.43				
66-80	1	2.86	9	25.71	2	5.71					
2	Gender										
	Male	4	11.43	15	42.86	4	11.43	2	0.29	0.865	Not significant
	Female	3	8.57	7	20.00	2	5.71				
Education status											
3	Illiterate	1	2.86	5	14.29	1	2.86	6	21.203	0.002	Significance
	Primary	0	0.00	14	40.00	5	14.29				
	High School	1	2.86	2	5.71	0	0.00				
	Graduate	5	14.29	1	2.86	0	0.00				
	PG & above	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00				

4	Type of family											
	Joint	3	8.57	16	45.71	4	11.43	2	2.106	0.349	Not significant	
	Nuclear	4	11.43	6	17.14	2	5.71					
5	Area of living											
	Urban	5	14.29	10	28.57	3	8.57	2	1.44	0.487	Not significant	
	Rural	2	5.71	12	34.29	3	8.57					
6	Occupation											
	Private Employee	4	11.43	8	22.86	3	8.57	6	4.925	0.55	Not significant	
	Government Employee	1	2.86	1	2.86	1	2.86					
	Farmer	0	0.00	8	22.86	1	2.86					
	Housewife	2	5.71	5	14.29	1	2.86					
7	Monthly income of the family											
	Below Rs 10000/-	0	0.00	2	5.71	0	0.00	8	14.121	0.079	Not significant	
	Rs. 10001-25000	1	2.86	12	34.29	1	2.86					
	Rs. 25001-Rs 40000	4	11.43	5	14.29	5	14.29					
	RS 40001 - 55000	1	2.86	0	0.00	0	0.00					
	Above Rs 55001 & Above	1	2.86	3	8.57	0	0.00					
8	Marital status											
	Unmarried	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	0.608	0.738	Not significant	
	Married	7	20.00	21	60.00	6	17.14					
	Separated	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00					
	Widow	0	0.00	1	2.86	0	0.00					
9	Type of cardiac surgery											
	CABG	6	17.14	18	51.43	6	17.14	4	2.152	0.708	Not significant	
	Heart valve repair &	1	2.86	2	5.71	0	0.00					

	replacem ent										
	Aneurys m repair	0	0.00	2	5.71	0	0.00				
	heart transplan t	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00				

The table 5 describes that, association of level of ICU psychosis among post operative cardiac patients in experimental group on posttest I with their demographic variables, the data reveals that the educational status p value were 0.002, found significant. There were no any other demographic variables such as age, gender, type of family, area of living, occupation, monthly income, marital status and type of cardiac surgery not found significant association between level of psychosis.

Table no 6: Association between level of ICU psychosis (2nd Day observation) with demographic variables among post operative cardiac patient under control group. N=35

Sr. No.	Demogr aphic Variabl es	Level of ICU Psychosis						df	Chi squa re Val ue	P Value	Significa nce
		Normal		Sub syndromal		Delirium					
		F	%	F	%	F	%				
1	Age in Years							6	3.49	0.745	Not significa nt
	20-35	0	0.00	1	2.86	0	0.00				
	36-50	0	0.00	5	14.29	4	11.43				
	51-65	1	2.86	12	34.29	4	11.43				
	66-80	0	0.00	4	11.43	4	11.43				
2	Gender							2	1.16 2	0.559	Not significa nt
	Male	1	2.86	12	34.29	8	22.86				
	Female	0	0.00	10	28.57	4	11.43				
3	Education status							6	20.1 97	0.003	Significa nce
	Illiterate	0	0.00	7	20.00	4	11.43				
	Primary	0	0.00	10	28.57	8	22.86				
	High School	0	0.00	4	11.43	0	0.00				
	Graduat e	1	2.86	1	2.86	0	0.00				
	PG & above	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00				
4	Type of family							2	2.59 3	0.273	Not significa nt
	Joint	0	0.00	16	45.71	9	25.71				
	Nuclear	1	2.86	6	17.14	3	8.57				
5	Area of living							2		0.521	
	Urban	1	2.86	11	31.43	5	14.29				

	Rual	0	0.00	11	31.43	7	20.00		1.306		Not significant
6	Occupation										
	Private Employee	0	0.00	7	20.00	6	17.14	6	13.814	0.03	Significance
	Government Employee	1	2.86	2	5.71	0	0.00				
	Farmer	0	0.00	8	22.86	2	5.71				
	Housewife	0	0.00	5	14.29	4	11.43				
7	Monthly income of the family										
	Below Rs 10000/-	0	0.00	2	5.71	3	8.57	8	39.77	0.000	Significance
	Rs. 10001-25000	0	0.00	11	31.43	8	22.86				
	Rs. 25001-40000	0	0.00	7	20.00	1	2.86				
	RS 40001 - 55000	0	0.00	2	5.71	0	0.00				
Above Rs 55001 & Above	1	2.86	0	0.00	0	0.00					
8	Marital status										
	Unmarried	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	0.573	0.751	Not significant
	Married	1	2.86	20	57.14	10	28.57				
	Seperate d	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00				
Widow	0	0.00	2	5.71	2	5.71					
9	Type of cardiac surgery										
	CABG	1	2.86	17	48.57	11	31.43	4	1.496	0.827	Not significant
Heart valve repair & replacement	0	0.00	4	11.43	1	2.86					

Aneurysm repair	0	0.00	1	2.86	0	0.00				
heart transplant	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00				

The table 6 describes that, association of level of ICU psychosis among post operative cardiac patients in control group on posttest I with their demographic variables, the data reveals that the educational status p value were 0.002, occupation p value is 0.03 and monthly income of the family p value is 0.000 found significant.

There were no any other demographic variables such as age, gender, type of family, area of living, marital status and type of cardiac surgery not found significant association between level of psychosis.

IV. DISCUSSION

The present study was executed to assess the effectiveness of modified ABCD bundle on ICU psychosis among post-operative cardiac patients. The findings of the study proved that there was a significant reduction in the level of ICU psychosis after the intervention modified ABCD bundle. The findings are discussed objective wise and presented below.

Frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic variables.

The selected demographic variables of the study were age, gender, educational status, types of family, area of living, occupation, monthly income, marital status and types of cardiac surgeries.

Similarly, other study finding shows that; a retrospective cohort study on to assess risk factors for delirium was done in hospital at Japan. Study results that Delirium occurred in 205 of 2168 patients (9.5%). Age, physical restraint, past history of a cerebrovascular disorder, malignancy, intensive care unit stay, pain, and high blood urea nitrogen value were significant risk factors for delirium in the multivariate analysis. Among these, age was the strongest factor, with an odds ratio for delirium of 12.953 in patients 75 years of age or older. The length of hospital stays and the mortality rates were higher in patients with delirium.¹⁰

Assessment of post-test level of ICU psychosis among the post-operative cardiac patients in experimental and control group.

The samples of the experimental group experienced reduced level of ICU psychosis. The findings revealed that modified ABCD bundle had an impact on reducing the level of ICU psychosis of the post-operative cardiac patients of the experimental group. The findings indicated that the hospital routine care does not have a beneficial effect on the level of ICU psychosis of the patients, among postoperative cardiac patients. The post-test findings indicated that samples from both the experimental and control group experienced ICU psychosis but there was significant difference between both of them showcasing the effect of modified ABCD bundle.

Similarly, other study finding shows that; an exploratory prospective study was done to assess delirium incidence, associated factors, and outcomes on 245 adult post operative cardiac patients for 3 months. Delirium was diagnosed by the Confusion Assessment Method. Study results revealed that Delirium developed in 9% (n = 22) of the sample. Study concludes, the risk factors associated with development of delirium were advanced age and increased duration of surgery.¹¹

Assessment of effectiveness of modified ABCD bundle on level of ICU psychosis among post-operative cardiac patients in the experimental and control group.

Study concludes at 5% level of significance and 34 degrees of freedom that the above data gives sufficient evidence to conclude that patients after receiving ABCD bundle of care is effective in preventing ICU psychosis. Hence reject null hypothesis and accept research hypothesis.

Similarly, other experimental study to assess the effectiveness of ABCDE bundle among ICU patients on prevalence of ICU psychosis. Through a retrospective data analysis which was done before and after implementation of ABCDE bundle. Total 159 records reviewed and the study concluded that the prevalence of ICU psychosis decreased significantly and the mean number of days of ICU psychosis decreased significantly $p < 0.01$ after ABCDE bundle implementation.¹²

Association between level of ICU psychosis among post-operative cardiac patients among experimental and control group with their selected demographic variables.

The association of level of ICU psychosis among post operative cardiac patients in experimental group with their demographic variables; age, gender, education status, type of family, area of living, occupation, monthly income, marital status and type of cardiac surgery. Chi-square was applied to compute the association between the 2nd POD day ICU psychosis and demographic variables. The data reveals that the chi value of education status was $\chi = 21.203$ with 6 degree of freedom and p value were 0.002, found significant. There were no any other demographic variables found association between level of psychosis.

Similarly, a survey on organizational characteristics associated with ICU liberation (ABCDEF) bundle implementation by adult ICUs in Michigan. There is also a significant dose-response effect between safety culture, a collaborative work environment, and overall bundle implementation. Study concludes that, results can be used to develop effective bundle implementation strategies that leverage safety culture, inter-professional collaboration, and routine checklist use in ICUs to improve bundle implementation and performance.¹³

V. CONCLUSION

The findings verified that modified ABCD bundle was very effective in reducing the level of ICU psychosis of patients who underwent cardiac surgery and can be used as a non-pharmacological measure to reduce ICU psychosis during ICU stay.

REFERENCES

- [1].Ms. Nijin Samuel, "Effectiveness of modified ABCD bundle on ICU psychosis among cardiac post-operative patients at a selected hospital setting in Chennai", October 2017.
- [2].Berman A., Koziar B., Erb G. (2008). *Fundamental of nursing: concept, process and practice*. (8th edition). India: Dorling Kindersley Publishers.
- [3].Basavanthappa, B.T. (2007). *Medical surgical nursing*. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers
- [4].Heymann A, Radke F, Schiemann A, et al., (2010). Delayed treatment of ICU psychosis increases the mortality rate in Intensive care unit patients. *Journal of International medical Research*, 38(5): 1584-1595
- [5].Potter. A., & Perry. A. (2005). *Fundamental of nursing*. New Delhi: Elsevier.
- [6].Usha Lee, MC Farling November 12,2016 ICU ICU psychosis is terrifying and incredibly common: The week. India.
- [7].Sudhamaniamma S. Indian National Magazine Report (2009 April) ICU psychosis nurse's challenge. *Nursing journal of India*.12(1):28-30

- [8]. Floriana Pinto, Biancofiore G. (2016) the ABCDE Bundle: A Survey of Nurses Knowledge and Attitudes in the Intensive Care Units of a National Teaching Hospital in Italy. *Journal of Dimensions of Critical Care Nursing*. 35(6):309- 314.
- [9]. Allan H Rooper, Robert H Brown. (2005). *Adams and Victor's principles of neurology* (8th edition). 2009. P.115-119
- [10]. Suresh K. Sharma, "Nursing Research and Statistics", third edition, Elsevier. 2014. P. 163-169.
- [11]. Kubota, Keisuke, Suzuki, et al (2018) Age is the Most Significantly Associated Risk Factor with the Development of Delirium in Patients Hospitalized for More Than Five Days in Surgical Wards May 2018 - Volume 267 - Issue 5 - p 874-877
- [12]. Abla Habeeb-Allah "Delirium post-cardiac surgery: Incidence and associated factors," *Am Heart J*. 2019 Dec;170(1):79-86, 86.
- [13]. Mandy Bounds, Stacey Kram, Karen Gabel et al. (2016). Effect of ABCDE bundle implementation on prevalence of ICU psychosis in intensive care unit patients. *Journal of American Association of Critical Care Nurses*, 87-93
- [14]. Barr J, Ghaferi AA, Costa DK, et al. Organizational Characteristics Associated With ICU Liberation (ABCDEF) Bundle Implementation by Adult ICUs in Michigan. *Crit Care Explor*. 2020 Aug 19;2(8):e0169.